

IDRISK - IMPROVING DATA QUALITY FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

Pedro Nabais¹, Paulo Carmona¹, Sarogini Monteiro¹, Filipa Melo de Vasconcelos¹, Patrícia Liberato¹, Maria da Graça Dias², Luísa Oliveira², Roberto Brazão², Francisco Ravasco², Darja Sokolić³, Sandra Bašić³, Sidney Tomé²

¹ASAE – Food Risks Division. Economic and Food Safety Authority. Lisbon. Portugal ²INSA – Food and Nutrition Department. National Institute of Health Doutor Ricardo Jorge. IP. Lisbon. Portugal ³HAPIH – Croatian Food Agency for Agriculture and Food. Osijek. Croatia.

IDRisk | Background

The National Data Management System (NDMS) called "PT-ON-DATA" was developed in Portugal under the implementation of the electronic transmission of contaminant data to EFSA using the Standard Sample Description information format SSD. The process, has allowed the electronic transmission to EFSA, contributing in this way to an improvement on the final quality, integrity and consistency of data.

"PT-ON-DATA", began in 2012 in the field of chemical contaminants, through the consortium formed by INSA and DGAV, in collaboration with ASAE, IPMA and INIAV.

In 2014/2015, the same consortium and partners tested a new EFSA data model, SSD2, on the effectiveness and suitability for harmonized data collection and reporting in various domains: chemical contaminants, pesticide residues, food additives, biological monitoring and veterinary drug residues.

In 2016/2017, HAPIH tested a new EFSA data model, SSD2, on the effectiveness and suitability for harmonized data collection and reporting in various domains: chemical contaminants, pesticide residues, food additives and veterinary drug residues.

Currently, "PT-ON-DATA", has features to load sampling as well as laboratory related data files containing sampling information and results of the analyses, respectively. It also allows the mapping and validation of the analytical data in SSD2 format; conduct research and statistics; extract results and report data to different authorities. In addition has the dynamic creation of electronic sampling forms, which permits through a mobile device, to fill in the information gathered in the field.

IDRisk | Team Members

- Economic and Food Safety Authority (ASAE)
- National Institute of Health Dr. Ricardo Jorge (INSA)
- Croatian Agency for Agriculture and Food (HAPIH)

Objectives:

- Improve/Restructure the dynamic sampling forms module
- Develop the application that will run on the mobile devices
- Prepare/Improve the existing system in order to receive the data submitted through the mobile app
- Prepare/Improve the existing system so real-time communication with the mobile devices that are on the field is possible
- Data filled in through the use of digital sampling forms, must be able to be exported to a physical format
- Investigate and implement other means to gather information via the mobile devices while on the field
- Implement interfaces between systems (NDMSs) so a two-way communication is possible
- Plan and implement an automatic PT.ON.DATA FoodEx2 classification system for sampling descriptions

IDRisk

Call reference: GP/EFSA/ENCO/2018/03
Call title: Partnering Grants

Application

Consortium for knowledge exchange between Portugal (ASAE, INSA) and Croatia (HAPIH).

Project

ID RISK

Development of the National System of Official Control Data Management

Real time data logging (digital forms)

Foodex 2 Samples Coding

Fast Data Transmission to EFSA

Database error reduction (better data quality)

Georeferencing data "in situ"

TASKS

Task 1: Project management and coordination

Task 2: Framework development

Task 3: Framework testing

Task 4: Sustainability and dissemination activities

Task 5: Quality assurance and impact evaluation

IDRisk | Main activities

Framework development and validation with a project pilot

The organization of an international workshop to evidence the results obtained under the extended version of PT.ON.DATA and to promote the development of critical mass thinking in these areas of expertise

Open-access publications, to ensure that the developed framework applied to National Sampling Plan will be available to other National Plans and to all scientific community and to political decision-makers

The organization of future training courses for the sampling brigades (BCA), risk managers and assessors, in order to maintain the knowledge, transfer to other institutions at national level

ASAE and HAPIH both commit to encourage the use of the developed solutions at EFSA's level. Also engage EFSA's interest in order to endorse the use of this solution.